

English Literary Texts as Instruments for Enhancing Democratic Values, Youth Leadership and Communication Skills: A Study of Soft Skills Development Perspective

Tanveer Gulab¹ & Dr. L.V. Padmarani Rao²

¹Research Scholar, PG Department of English & Research Centre, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded.

²Research Supervisor, Professor and Head, PG Department of Research, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded.

Corresponding Author – Tanveer Gulab

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Abstract:

Literature is the reflection of a society. It presents society in an artistic way. Literature brings harmony in the society and it can also lead to revolution among individuals. Hence, the role of literature is not merely to let readers read the texts rather, it enlightens their minds. As the Indian Constitution is itself a written document and it teaches values to its citizens such as equality, fraternity, brotherhood, dignity towards women and living beings in general. It also promotes freedom for all, right to privacy and protection to life as a core of its heart. Hence, the law of the land is also a prosperous socio-cultural text that has written according to the needs and futuristic vision of the society.

Further, the values that has discussed above are protected in the constitution but there are some other skills called as soft skills which needs to be develop, tested and inculcated to survive in the society. These skills include communication skills, leadership skills, emotional intelligence skills, empathy, critical thinking, decision-making and many other skills. All these skills are part of life skills, and the word 'life' is itself highlights the importance of soft skills in life. Hence, these skills bring harmony, prosperity and scientific temper in the life of individuals which gets reflected in the society.

Hence, the role of English literary texts as a medium or a tool to develop soft skills and enhancing democratic values, youth leadership and communication skills is crucial. Using mixed, analytical, critical approach these paper tries to shift the attention of the audience towards the literary texts as a competent literary laboratory. Hence, literature is not merely a text but it has context, cultural values, societal harmony and it also brings positivity among learners.

Keywords: Soft Skills, Life Skills, English Literary Texts, Democratic Values, Youth Leadership and Communication Skills.

Introduction:

In contemporary world, almost all the countries are carrying their own past legacy that highlights their struggles to become a modern civilized nation. All the countries run their nations at present with the help of some rules, regulations, norms, laws and acts. To run the legislative, administrative, executive stuff and every day's business the authority has required

some functional structures and societal conscience. Hence, to bring societal values, cultural aspects, and emerging needs of nation literature can help vividly. English literature is a literature that has wider global audience. Soon after colonization in India English became the language of educational mainstream and other activities. Hence, English has got tremendous significance; English overpower other vernacular

languages in mainstream. The process of becoming a free nation required to understand the pain that has carried by people of the nation languages together.

After decolonization, English language become did not lost the significance but it became the voice for marginalized, deserted, and unheard people and communities to express their belief, faith, thoughts, worship, pain and struggles along with harsh reality in the society they had witnessed. Hence, English language gave the power of expression to people through its literary texts and artistic world. In the process of globalization, whole world became one connected, common and global village, where English became the global language. Hence, English literary texts became an Instrument to develop and nurture certain essential traits required for human development and to make a nation more prosperous such as democratic values, youth leadership and communication skills etc. Thus, literature is the social laboratory and knowledge of hub to develop, test, inculcate and nurture soft skills. Therefore, literature becomes an effective educational tool for developing both academic knowledge and life skills.

Literature Review:

The literature review highlights the significance of literature and its core values. It considers literature as a powerful tool to bring moral and social education; literature as a medium for soft skills development yet there is a gap that needs to be addressed.

A. Early Perspective: Literature as Moral and Social Education:

Early scholars emphasized that literature plays an essential role in shaping human values and ethical understanding. Literature enables readers to explore human experiences, and capabilities, moral dilemmas, and social

relationships. Louise Rosenblatt stated that, 'reading literature is a transactional process in which readers interact with texts to construct meaning and develop emotional and intellectual responses. This interaction helps readers develop empathy, moral awareness, and social understanding' (Rosenblatt, 1978).

Similarly, Martha C. Nussbaum argues that literature contributes to democratic citizenship by encouraging individuals to imagine the experiences of others, develop compassion and ethical reasoning (Nussbaum, 1997). These early perspectives highlight the connection between literature and the development of democratic values. It also demonstrates the role of literary works to understand soft skills.

B. Literature and Language Communication Skills:

It has been widely recognized by the researchers that literature is an effective tool for improving communication skills. Literary texts expose learners to authentic language use and complex linguistic structures and primary understanding of these skills. Through reading, interpretation, and discussion, students develop vocabulary, comprehension, and expressive abilities.

Further, studies also show that teaching literature in language classrooms improves both written and oral communication skills. It also encourages students to articulate ideas, participate in discussions, and express interpretations of texts, thereby strengthening communicative competence (Ilankumaran & Deepa, 2018).

Furthermore, literature enhances critical reading and analytical writing, which are essential components of effective communication (Sharma et al., 2022).

C. Emergence of Soft Skills in Educational Research:

The concept of soft skills, in recent decades, has gained significant importance in

educational and professional contexts. Soft skills include interpersonal communication, leadership, teamwork, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence.

Research suggests that these skills are essential for both academic success and employability. It also highlights employers consider communication, teamwork, integrity, and leadership among the most important competencies required in the workplace (Robles, 2012). Further, the research emphasizes that soft skills contribute significantly to personal and professional development (Heckman and Kautz, 2012).

As a result, modern education increasingly focuses on integrating soft skills development into teaching and learning processes.

D. Literature as a Medium for Soft Skills Development:

Recent studies indicate that literature is an effective tool for developing soft skills among students. Literary texts encourage critical thinking, empathy, creativity, and collaboration. It has found that literature-based learning activities such as group discussions, role play, and textual interpretation promote communication skills, teamwork, and confidence among students. These activities also encourage students to express opinions, analyze social issues and perspectives, and develop interpersonal skills (Haxhihseni and Roseni, 2025).

Further, with similar views the research has argued that teaching English literature helps learners develop emotional intelligence and social awareness, which are essential aspects of soft skills (Islam and Das, 2024).

E. Literature and Youth Leadership Development:

Leadership development among youth is closely linked with the cultivation of soft skills. Literary texts often portray characters who

demonstrate courage, capabilities, responsibility, and ethical leadership.

By analyzing such characters, students learn leadership qualities such as decision-making, moral responsibility, and problem-solving. Literature-based discussions also encourage collaborative learning, where students practice leadership and teamwork within classroom environments (Robles, 2012).

Thus, research indicates that literature provides opportunities for students to reflect on leadership models and develop their own leadership identity.

F. Literature and Democratic Values:

Society and on the other hand, democratic values such as equality, justice, freedom, and social responsibility are frequently explored in literary works. Through literary narratives, students' active participation to understand social issues and develop critical perspectives on power, authority, and justice.

Hence, recent research studies emphasizes that literature plays a crucial role in democratic education because it encourages individuals to understand diverse perspectives and develop empathy toward others (Nussbaum, 1997).

By discussing themes such as injustice, discrimination, and social responsibility, literature promotes civic awareness and encourages responsible citizenship.

G. Contemporary Studies on Soft Skills and Education:

Recent educational research highlights the increasing importance of soft skills in modern society. Further, scholars argue that communication, adaptability, collaboration, and emotional intelligence are essential competencies for the twenty-first century workforce.

One of the researcher notes that educational institutions are increasingly incorporating soft skills training into curricula

through interactive and collaborative teaching methods (Coelho and Martins, 2022).

These approaches align closely with literature-based teaching strategies, which encourage dialogue, interpretation, analysis and critical reflection among students.

Thus, the review of existing literature shows that English literary texts play a significant role in developing communication skills, leadership qualities, and democratic values. Early scholars emphasized the moral and social impact of literature, while contemporary studies highlight its effectiveness in fostering soft skills essential for personal and professional development.

Therefore, integrating English literary texts into educational practices can contribute significantly to the development of democratic values, youth leadership, and communication skills through the cultivation of soft skills. Hence, it is crucial to understand the role of literature to develop and enhance soft skills as well.

English Literary Texts and Development of Soft Skills:

It is rightly that 'Literature is the criticism of life.' Literature represents society and social reality by bringing literary aspects related to society in reality literature cultivates social consciousness among individual learners. Literature is an artistic medium of expressing cultural values, societal harmony and distress.

Literature can be written or oral in forms. It can also be written in various genres such as poetry, fiction, non-fiction, drama or plays etc. Literature can be, as short as a line of a poem or it can be as broad as an epic poem. It can be a real-life-based piece of a literary work called as non-fiction or it can also be known as a fictional work which is based on imaginative life. It can also be a fictional work with real life experienced based narration of evidences. Hence, literature has a

critical role to play, its essential understanding play a crucial role.

English literature is also an efficient tool to develop soft skills as it brings characters in real life, thus, readers and learners can understand the essential values and connect it to real life. Hence, literature is a laboratory to nurture soft skills such as communication skills, leadership skills, cultural sensitivity, empathy and emotional intelligence. Thus, English literary texts function as an instrument for enhancing democratic values, youth leadership and communication skills. This can be understood in the following ways.

A. English Literature and Democratic Values:

Every civilization has witnessed a progress when it was marching ahead with values and democratic independence and on the other hand, civilizations without values got destroyed. And literature has cherished these moments since ages. Hence literature especially English literature is an efficient tool to develop soft skills.

As literature through its various characters, actions, dialogues and settings depict the role of literature in bringing democratic values such as Literature enhances brotherhood such as in Mahesh Dattani's *Final Solution*, a play, the characters of Bobby, Smita and Ramnik through their actions bring brotherhood, depicts common values. They respect each-others culture, social norms and traditions. Which reading and teaching such incidences in classroom, it instills new perspective in learners' minds and hence, that further shapes readers attitude. Hence, the understanding of literature brings more values such as:

- It makes learners aware about social realities.
- It brings new perspective in the minds of readers.
- It highlights social significance of individual actions.

- It brings cultural awareness and differences to be get respected from each-other.
- It demonstrates empathy, secularism, equality and enlightens the minds of learners.

It can be taught through group discussion, role play, Book Culture discussions etc.

Thus, English literature brings positivity in the minds of young learners and enlightens the minds of others.

B. English Literature and Youth Leadership:

English literature demonstrates diversity in situations, settings, actions of characters. Hence, it provides appropriate platform to develop leadership skills. As in a play *Final Solutions* written by Mahesh Dattani, the characters of Bobby and Javed shown as a characters who were suffering from communal violence helped by Ramnik's family in the turmoil of partition in India. This play depicts how Bobby has saved one idol and respected cultures. This incidence was one of the common instances but at the time of partition and communal violence this act was rare. Hence, it can be considered that English literature is competent enough to bring youth leadership. IT also highlights some of the other aspects of leadership such as:

- It make individuals aware about situations.
- Critical thinking and decision-making can be seen in leadership traits.
- It make individual to understand the values each preserve as a core.
- It brings enlightenment among young learners.

Leadership traits can be taught in through group discussion, engaging workshops, study of characters from play etc. Thus, the role of literature is vivid to provide more insights about such skills.

C. English Literature and Communication Skills

Communication skills are the soft part of human behavior. It can make the deal or break it. Communication can be intrapersonal that is talking to oneself or interpersonal that is talking or communicating or interacting with others. Hence, communication skill is a key soft skill. It highlights the role of literature as its essential aspect as through literature characters get resolution of their issues and problem of ever day's life. To mention, Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* (1813) was one of the well-known novels. It depicts how the misunderstanding of Elizabeth, a protagonist of this novel leads to a gap and false consideration about Mr. Darcy, a protagonist of the same novel. Towards the end through communication their misunderstanding gets resolve. Hence, literature can play a crucial role and demonstrates

- Communication as a key skill which can be effectively inculcated and developed from English literature.
- It highlights social awareness among people about their livings and cultures.
- It represents role of values that individuals cherish.
- It signifies the strength of effective communication.

All these can be nurtured through debates, groups-discussions and role play. Poster presentation can also be made to develop these skills. Thus, the role of English literature is significant to develop soft skills.

Soft Skills Development and Teaching Strategies:

Literature is a mirror of society. It reflects social values and cultural consciousness Soft skills are a part of human values, characters and personality. As these skills are different from hard skills, soft skills are non-technical in nature they

can be learned by anyone at any point of time. On the other hand hard skills are technical in nature; they are job specific, and can be learned in a specific environment. Hence, soft skills complement hard skills both crucial for growth and development Thus, it is crucial to understand and teach soft skills to make an equal, prosperous and progressive nation

Furthermore, soft skills are related to human character, human traits and human personality. These skills are crucial to bring career-centric opportunities. Thus, these skills play a vital role to develop any nation, bring harmony and make the nation stronger through soft diplomacy. As soft skills provide

- Deeper understanding of human behavior.
- These skills demonstrate positive values such as empathy and kindness.
- These skills enlighten young learners to adapt to new culture with sensitivity.
- These skills enhance perspectives of individuals; further, each broadens understanding of society which will lead to human understanding.
- Soft skills such as emotional intelligence and empathy can reflect society well; hence, nation-building will be there.

Thus, it can be said that soft skills are crucial to understand the needs of the nation, and make the country more progressive. Hence, it is crucial to understand the role of skills while teaching. Teaching these skills in classroom is required certain strategies which can be understood in the following representation.

Soft Skills	Literary Aspects	Classroom Teaching
Democratic Values and attitude	Attitude of characters; dialogues	Role Play and Assignment
Youth Leadership	Actions taken by characters in various situations	Group Discussion
Communication	Dialogues,	Role play,

Skills	verbal and non-verbal sings by characters	Debate
Critical Thinking	Role played by characters in different situations	Short clips of novels in audio-visual form and Role play
Decision-Making	Role played; and their actions by characters in different situations	Paper Reading, Quizzes, Seminars and Debate
Emotional Intelligence and Empathy	Shown in a literary texts through lines, explanation, or via characters	Short films, Role Play

Fig. 1: A Study of Soft Skills Development Perspective

Figure 1 demonstrates various soft skills, their literary perspectives and teaching them in classroom. Soft skills are core of human personality the above representation shows how soft skills are crucial to be studied and performed. Teaching such skills in classroom enhances learners’ cognitive competence, and their understanding towards society. Thus, it is crucial to develop and inculcate these skills in classroom teaching.

As these skills foster:

- Individual understanding towards society.
- They make learners aware about their social stands.
- These skills make learners to understand social values and it brings deeper understanding about it.
- They enhance democratic attitude among learners.
- They bring essential traits to lead the team, groups and a nation as well.
- They foster strategic communication skills.

- They lead to soft diplomacy at larger level.

Thus, the role of soft skills development through literature is unique, crucial, vital and need of the hour. As in Western influence the world has learned that soft skills are employability skills. But the eastern education system considers soft skills as a part of life and individual human character. Hence, English literature bridges the gap and leads to the development of soft skills for national progress.

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